

Role of Antyodaya Anna Yojana in Ensuring Food Security : A Case Study of Banka District, Bihar

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Abstract

The Antyodaya Anna Yojana (Antyodaya Anna Yojana) is a significant scheme for ensuring food security for poor families in India. Its objective is to provide affordable food grains to the poorest families in the country. This scheme is a significant and effective initiative towards ensuring food security in India. This scheme is particularly important in backward districts of poor and backward states like Bihar, where problems of poverty, malnutrition, and unemployment persist. Therefore, the importance of this scheme in ensuring food security in Banka district, one of the backward districts of Bihar, is even greater. The present study examines the role of the Antyodaya Anna Yojana in Banka district and finds that the timely availability of food grains to benefiting families has significantly improved food security, consumption, and poverty levels.

Keywords

Antyodaya Anna Yojana, Public Distribution System, Poverty, Food Security.

Introduction

Food security means ensuring the availability of adequate, nutritious, and safe food for all sections of society. To promote food security in India, the Government of India enacted the Food Security Act, 2013. Its three main objectives are to ensure food availability, food access, and adequate food intake and nutrition. Like the Antyodaya Anna Yojana, the Food Security Scheme aims to provide affordable food to the poor and vulnerable. Since India is a diverse and large country with agriculture as its primary occupation, the problems of poverty, hunger, and malnutrition have long existed due to the reliance primarily on agriculture for employment and livelihood. The Government of India has recognized these challenges for society and the country and has launched various schemes and programs to provide essential food items to the people, thus effectively addressing these social problems. Among these important government schemes, the Antyodaya Anna Yojana and the Food Security Scheme are crucial. Both these schemes were launched by the government to uplift the poor and underprivileged.

Public Distribution System

The Public Distribution System (PDS) was established in the 1980s to provide for the public distribution of essential commodities during the war in India, which had led to a severe food shortage. To prevent the rise in food prices and ensure the availability of food grains to the people, the PDS was established. To this day, it controls food price rises and black marketing, strengthening food security in India. As agricultural production increased after the Green Revolution, the Public Distribution System (PDS) expanded to rural and remote areas. The Public Distribution System (PDS) distributes various food items in India, including wheat, rice, sugar, and kerosene. Some states and union territories also distribute large quantities of cereals, oil, pulses, iodized salt, spices, and other essential commodities through the Public Distribution System (PDS). This distribution system is jointly operated by the Government of India and state governments. The Government of India uses the Public Distribution System as a tool to ensure food security. The Public Distribution System is a robust nationwide distribution network that distributes various government services related to food grains to the poor and needy people of the country. Currently, the Government of India is modernizing all the Public Distribution Systems.

There is a direct link between poverty and hunger. Poor families do not have enough income to purchase sufficient nutritious food for themselves and their families. The Antyodaya Anna Yojana (Antyodaya Anna Yojana) provides food grains to poor families at affordable prices, addressing the problem of access to nutritious food and strengthening food security in India.

Need of the Study

Food security is a major challenge in modern times, where unemployment, malnutrition, poverty, and multidimensional poverty are widespread. The objective of this scheme is to ensure affordable food grains for the country's poorest families. The social and economic disparities and diversity of Banka district, along with the high number of vulnerable groups, make it essential to study this scheme.

Objective of study

1. To study the role of Antyodaya Anna Yojana in ensuring food security of extremely poor families in Banka district.
2. To present concrete suggestions to make the presented scheme more effective, inclusive and transparent.
3. To study the economic impact of this scheme on the beneficiary families.
4. To study the impact of this scheme on improving the actual condition of the poor.

Review of Literature

1. **Varadarajan B. et al. (2012)** studied the impact of the Antyodaya Anna Yojana on the food security of the poorest families in poverty. They found that the scheme plays a significant role in India's socio-economic development. This study is based primarily on secondary data collected from research papers published in various national and international journals, dissertations, government reports, and books published by various publications. The present study examines key issues such as food grain shortages and inefficient management in the Public Distribution System. Various statistical techniques, such as mean, percentage-wise inference, value, and SPSS, were used. This study demonstrates that the central government, through the FCI, has delegated the responsibility of procurement, counciling, and distribution of food grains to state governments. Based on the analysis of secondary data in this study, it is clear that the Antyodaya Anna Yojana (Antyodaya Anna Yojana) was launched in December 2000 for India's population living below the poverty line. This scheme promotes the implementation of the National Diet and improves nutrition levels.
2. **Nirala and Jaitpuri (2013)** conducted an analytical study of the right to food in the Indian context in their research study, "The Right to Food: A Human Right," and concluded that all people have an equal right to food. Therefore, it is essential to ensure adequate food supply for all.
3. **Raja Shabbi (2013)** examined the role of the Antyodaya Anna Yojana (Antyodaya Anna Yojana) in ensuring food security in rural Uttar Pradesh. He found that the Antyodaya Anna Yojana (Antyodaya Anna Yojana) is a key scheme in India's public distribution system, operational since 2000. The scheme promotes food security by providing affordable food grains to the poorest of the poor. He emphasized the need to provide free food grains to the poorest of the poor in society to ensure food security.
4. **Chinnadurai (2014)** in his research study on the saline drought of poor families in Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh and Uttarakhand. The impact of the Antyodaya Anna Yojana was studied. This study is based primarily on primary data. Data collection was conducted by randomly selecting two blocks from one district in each state. To study the Antyodaya Anna Yojana, the distribution list of beneficiaries of the Antyodaya Anna Yojana (Public Distribution System) was obtained from two blocks in each district. 100 Antyodaya Anna Yojana beneficiaries were selected from each Public Distribution System. The data was analyzed using various statistical techniques. The data collection was found to have a positive impact on the food security and nutrition of poor families in these states. The study also found some shortcomings in the scheme that need to be addressed.
5. **Das Pawan (2025)** in his research study on the impact of Antyodaya Anjana and public distribution system in banka district, found that the implementation of the scheme improved the economic condition of beneficiary families, positively impacting their income, expenditure, and savings. The study also found that the consumption and savings capacity of beneficiary families increased. However, he also noted some problems associated with the scheme, which need to be addressed. This scheme is very important from the perspective of poverty alleviation and food security in India, and has had a positive impact on the economic and social status of poor families in India.

Methodology

Research Study Method

The present research study is based on primary and secondary data. This study examines the role of the Antyodaya Anna Yojana in ensuring human well-being. Primary data were collected using a systematic method from 100 selected Antyodaya Anna Yojana beneficiaries in rural areas of Banka district. Charts, tables, percentages, and graphs were used to analyze the data.

**Role of Antyodaya Anna Yojana in ensuring food security
Demographic details of the respondents**

Table:-1.0

Gender based classification of respondents		
Sex	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Male	67	67 %
Female	33	33 %
Total	100	100%
Age based classification of respondents		
Age group	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Up to 30 years	06	06 %
31-45 years	40	40 %
46-60 years	44	44 %
More than 60 years	10	10 %
Total	100	100 %
classification of respondents on marital status		
Marital status	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Married	93	9 %
Unmarried	07	07 %
Total	100	100 %
Education based classification of respondents		
Education level	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Illiterate	25	25 %
10 th	30	30 %
12 ^{tjh}	35	35 %
Graduate and above	10	10 %
Total	100	100%
Income level based classification of respondents		
Income level (RS.)	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Up to 6000	13	13 %
6000 - 8000	25	25 %
8000 -10,000	20	20 %
10,000 -12,000	20	20 %
More than 12,000	22	22%
Total	100	100 %

Classification based on the food grains made available at the Public Distribution System shop under Atyodaya Anna Yojana : _

In the present study, information was collected and analyzed about the services being provided by the Public Distribution System to a total of 300 selected beneficiaries of Antyodaya Anna Yojana, which is displayed in the following Table-1.1 and Chart-1.1.

Table:-1.1

name of food grains	Number of respondents	Percentage respondent	of total respondents
Rice	100	100%	100
wheat	100	100%	100
Sugar	10	10%	100
kerosene oil	04	04%	100
other essential items	00	00%	100

(Source: Primary data)

Chart-1.1

It is clear from the above table and chart that a total of 100 selected beneficiary respondents are provided rice and wheat through the public distribution system. Out of the selected beneficiary respondents of Antyodaya Anna Yojana, only 10 percent respondents said that sugar is made available to them. Whereas, out of a total of 100 selected respondents, 04 percent respondents said that apart from wheat and rice, kerosene oil is also made available to them.

Hence, it is clear from the above studies that in the study area, mainly rice and wheat are provided to the beneficiary families of Antyodaya Anna Yojana through the public distribution system.

Respondents' views regarding timely supply of food grains under Antyodaya Anna Yojana

In the present study area, to study the timely supply of food grains being made available through the Public Distribution System under Antyodaya Anna Yojana in Banka district, questions were asked to the beneficiary respondents and the answers received have been displayed through the following Table-1.2 and Chart 1.2.

Timely supply of food grains	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondent
Yes	63	63%
No	23	23%
Don't say	14	14%
Total	100	100%

(Source: Primary data)

Chart-1.2

The table and chart above clearly show that of the 100 beneficiary respondents included in the study, 63 percent reported timely food grain delivery through the Public Distribution System. Meanwhile, 23 percent reported that food grains are not delivered on time. A further 14 percent expressed neutral views on this issue.

Therefore, based on the above study, it is clear that food grains provided under the Antyodaya Anna Yojana are delivered on time in the study area. However, in some areas or locations, timely supply is difficult.

Respondents' opinion regarding ensuring food security of poor families due to Antyodaya Anna Yojana

Table 1.3 presents the analysis of the food security related data of the beneficiary families of Atyodya Anna Yojana, which has been obtained from the beneficiary respondents selected in this study.

Table -1.3

Ensure food security to poor families.	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondent
Perfectly disagree	03	03%
disagree	14	14%
Neutral	17	17%
agree	37	37%
Perfectly agree	29	29%
Total	100	100%

(Source: Primary data)

Char

It is clear from the above table and chart that out of total 100 beneficiary respondents included in the study, 03 percent respondents completely disagreed with the fact that food security of poor families has been ensured by getting the benefits of this scheme. 14 percent respondents have expressed their disagreement with the fact that food security of poor families has been ensured by the implementation of this scheme. Whereas 17 percent respondents have neutral opinion on this matter. 37 percent respondents have expressed their agreement that food security of poor families has been ensured by the implementation of this scheme. Whereas 87 (29 percent) out of total respondents have expressed their complete agreement that food security of poor families has been ensured.

Hence, from the above analysis it is clear that out of the total respondents included in the study, maximum 66 percent respondents have agreed that the implementation of this scheme has ensured food security of the beneficiary poor families.

Details of respondents regarding the economic crisis caused to the poor due to the closure of Antyodaya Anna Yojana-

Table 1.4 presents the analysis of the answers obtained by asking selected beneficiary respondents of the Atyodya Anna Yojana to study what impact the closure of the scheme could have on the poor.

Table -1.4

Opinion on the impact of discontinuation of the scheme on the poor	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Perfectly disagree	4	4%
disagree	3	3%
Neutral	17	17%
agree	43	43%
Perfectly agree	33	33%
Total	100	100%

(Source: Primary data)

Chart-1

It is clear from the above table and chart that out of the total 300 beneficiary respondents included in the study, 04 percent respondents completely disagreed with the fact that closure of this scheme may cause financial crisis to the beneficiary. 03 percent)respondents have expressed their disagreement with the fact that closure of this scheme may cause financial crisis to the beneficiary. Whereas 17 percent respondents have neutral opinion on this matter. 43 percent respondents have expressed their agreement that closure of this scheme may cause financial crisis to the beneficiary. Out of the total respondents, 33 percent respondents have expressed their complete agreement that closure of this scheme may cause financial crisis to the beneficiary families.

Therefore, the above analysis reveals that a maximum of 70 percent respondents agreed that if the scheme were discontinued, the Sabhadhi families would face financial hardship.

Details of respondents regarding improvement in the actual condition of the poor due to Atyodaya Anna Yojana -

Table 1.5 presents the analysis of the data related to improvement in the actual condition of the poor families benefiting from Antyodaya Anna Yojana, which has been obtained from the beneficiary respondents selected in this study.

Table -1.5

Opinion regarding improvement in the actual situation due to the scheme	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Perfectly disagree	05	05%
disagree	15	15%
Neutral	20	20%
agree	43	43%
Perfectly agree	17	17%
Total	100	100%

(Source: Primary data)
Chart-1.5

It is clear from the above table and chart that out of total 100 beneficiary respondents included in the study, 06 percent respondents have completely disagreed with the fact that their actual condition has improved after getting the benefits of this scheme. 15 percent respondents have expressed their disagreement with the fact that their actual condition has improved after the implementation of this scheme. Whereas 20 percent respondents have neutral opinion on this matter. 43 percent respondents have expressed their agreement that their actual condition has improved after the implementation of this scheme. Whereas 17 percent out of total respondents have expressed their complete agreement that their actual condition has improved.

Hence, from the above analysis it is clear that out of the total respondents included in the study, maximum 60 percent respondents have agreed that the implementation of this scheme has improved the actual condition of the beneficiary poor families.

Conclusion

The present study examined the impact of the Antyodaya Anna Yojana on the food security of the poorest of the poor families. The study found that this scheme plays a significant role in India's socio-economic development. The study demonstrates that the central government, through the FCI, has delegated the responsibility of procuring, transporting, and distributing food grains to state governments. The study found that the Antyodaya Anna Yojana is a key scheme in India's public distribution system, operational since 2000. Providing affordable food grains to the poorest of the poor families under this scheme promotes food security. It emphasizes the need to provide free food grains to the poorest of the poor in society to ensure their well-being. This scheme has had a positive impact on the food security and nutrition of poor families in these states. The study also found that some shortcomings regarding the distribution and timely availability of food grains in this scheme need to be addressed.

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